

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Karimov Ilhomjon

Teacher of computer science at school No. 2, Namangan district,
Namangan region.

Turganov Otabek

Teacher of computer science at school No. 2, Namangan district,
Namangan region.

Hamidov Abdusattar

Teacher of computer science at school No. 2, Namangan district,
Namangan region.

Abstract: What are the advantages and disadvantages of currently developing artificial intelligence for us, negative and positive effects for the future of humanity.

Key words: artificial intelligence, innovation, security, neutrality, cons and pros, technology related, privacy issues.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence is a branch of computer science that deals with the development of software systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence. Such systems use machine learning methods and algorithms to help them develop and make their own decisions based on information received from the external environment. Artificial intelligence is used in various fields such as medicine, finance, manufacturing, transportation, etc. It has great

potential to automate tasks and increase labor productivity, which makes it an important tool for the development of modern technologies. Artificial intelligence is needed to solve complex problems that the human mind cannot solve quickly and efficiently. It can be used in various fields, from banking and finance to medicine and science. Artificial intelligence can also help automate processes, improve quality of life, and create new products and services. It can be used to build smart offices, autonomous vehicles, medical diagnostic systems, and more. The development of artificial intelligence is one of the main areas of technology development that can bring great benefits to mankind.

Increase efficiency:

One of the most important advantages of artificial intelligence is to increase the efficiency of processes. Artificial intelligence can perform mundane and repetitive tasks, allowing humans to focus on more specialized and creative work.

Cost reduction:

By automating processes and optimizing workflows with artificial intelligence, companies can reduce costs associated with manual labor, human error, and waste. Operating costs can also be reduced.

Improved decision making:

Artificial intelligence can analyze large amounts of data in real time, providing companies with insights and patterns that humans cannot detect. This information helps make better decisions in all aspects of the company.

Enhanced customer experience:

Artificial intelligence can be used to personalize and customize the customer experience. In e-commerce, AI can recommend products based on customer browsing history and purchasing behavior, leading to increased sales and customer satisfaction.

Innovation:

Artificial intelligence allows enterprises to explore new areas and opportunities that were previously impossible or too expensive; leading to innovation and potential industry disruption.

24/7 Availability:

AI doesn't need to rest or sleep, and that means businesses can work around the clock.

Security:

Artificial intelligence systems can monitor and identify potential security threats in real time, helping to prevent cyber attacks, data breaches or unauthorized access. It provides security in critical facilities such as airports, hospitals and nuclear facilities.

Change of job:

Artificial intelligence can automate low-level tasks performed by humans such as data entry and processing, which can lead to significant job displacement.

Neutrality:

Algorithms used in artificial intelligence systems can be programmed with flawed programs that reflect the biases and biases of their creators.

Lack of emotional intelligence:

Artificial intelligence lacks empathy and emotional intelligence, which are necessary to understand and respond to human emotions.

Risks:

Artificial intelligence can be used by criminals or malicious actors to launch attacks, increasing security threats.

Dependence on technology:

Dependence on artificial intelligence technology can lead to a decrease in critical thinking and creativity in people.

Privacy Issues:

Artificial intelligence systems rely on personal information and data, which can compromise privacy and security.

Moral and Ethical Concerns:

Artificial intelligence technology raises ethical and moral concerns around issues of security, transparency, and accountability.

Cost:

Developing and maintaining AI systems can be expensive, which can limit the use of the technology for small businesses and organizations.

Restrictions:

Artificial intelligence is limited by the data and algorithms it uses and may not be able to adapt to new situations or complex tasks.

Lack of human interaction:

Using AI technology in a social context can lead to a lack of human interaction and potential isolation.

Based on the opinion and research of experts, we will show some good and bad effects of artificial intelligence for the future.

Pros:

Artificial intelligence takes over repetitive and mundane tasks and frees up human resources for higher-level decision-making.

Artificial intelligence has the potential to alleviate some of the world's most pressing problems, such as climate change and poverty, by analyzing data in real-time to create more efficient systems.

improved healthcare through AI predictive analytics, personalized treatment recommendations and medical image analysis.

Enhanced security in a variety of industries, including self-driving cars, predictive maintenance in manufacturing, and cyber security.

Cons:

Increasing automation may lead to job displacement, particularly in areas such as manufacturing, transportation, and data entry.

Artificial intelligence has inherent risks of increasing bias and discrimination, which can lead to unfair decisions, particularly in the areas of employment, credit and criminal justice.

Increased reliance on AI can lead to a lack of transparency and accountability, especially when AI makes critical decisions that affect human lives.

the potential for malicious use of artificial intelligence, particularly in the areas of surveillance, cyberattacks, and weaponization. In general, the future impact of artificial intelligence will depend on how it is developed and implemented. If AI is developed ethically, with privacy and security in mind, it has the potential to greatly improve society.

However, if artificial intelligence is developed recklessly, without proper regulations and controls, it can pose a great threat to humanity. Here is an overview of some of the debates and opinions of scientists on the development and destruction of artificial intelligence.

Scientists have different opinions about the future of artificial intelligence. Some argue that AI could change society in positive ways, such as automating simple tasks, improving health outcomes, and increasing efficiency in areas such as manufacturing and transportation.

Others are more cautious, warning of the potential negative effects of AI, such as the displacement of human workers, the perpetuation of prejudice, and the creation of new forms of inequality. There are also concerns that the manipulation and control of artificial intelligence by malicious actors can lead to dangerous consequences.

Several experts, including Elon Musk and Stephen Hawking, have warned about the possible dangers of uncontrolled development of artificial intelligence. Musk went so far as to describe AI as "more dangerous than nuclear weapons" and called for more regulation and oversight of AI development.

However, other scientists argue that such concerns are overblown and that the development of artificial intelligence should continue without unnecessary restrictions. They argue that the potential benefits of AI far outweigh the risks, and that proper training and regulations can help prevent negative consequences.

In general, the debates and opinions of scientists reflect a complex and evolving understanding of the potential benefits and drawbacks of artificial intelligence. It remains to be seen how the development of

artificial intelligence will continue in the coming years and what the ultimate impact on society will be.

References:

1. <https://fayllar.org/guruh-askarov-abror-mavzu-suniy-intellektni-rivojlanish-tarixi.html> .
2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sun-iy-intellekt-va-uning-asosida-yaratilgan-texnologiyalar-tahlili> .
3. <https://fayllar.org/mavzu-suniy-intellektning-rivojlanishi-ijobiy-va-salbiy-jihat.html> .
4. <https://daryo.uz/2023/03/29/insoniyat-uchun-tahdid-ilon-mask-suniy-intellekt-boyicha-tajribalarni-toxtatishga-chaqirdi>.
5. <https://daryo.uz/k/2017/04/30/stiven-xoking-suniy-intellektda-insoniyat-halokatiga-tahdidni-kordi>.